

Introduction: The recent surge in lunar exploration underscores the growing imperative for robust access to the lunar surface. This is reflected in current space strategies, with missions increasingly focusing on surface operations that demand precise and reliable landing systems to enable in-situ analysis and experimentation [1, 2]. However, successful surface operations in critical regions like the lunar poles or far side are heavily constrained by limited Earth visibility and extreme illumination conditions. Evaluating low-altitude hazards and planning safe surface mobility require sub-meter resolution imagery, yet existing orbital image archives often lack the necessary resolution, lighting variability, or perspective diversity. Consequently, the development of robust hazard avoidance strategies requires large datasets of realistic, high-resolution synthetic images of the application scenario, accurately reproducing planetary topography, reflectance, and albedo.

To address this need, this work proposes a novel rendering pipeline for generating high-fidelity synthetic optical images of the lunar surface, aimed at supporting mission planning, hazard assessment, and the validation of autonomous navigation systems for both landing and surface mobility operations. While generally applicable to any location on the Moon, the framework specifically accounts for the unique characteristics of the lunar poles, which are of particular scientific value and interest for future missions. These regions pose significant challenges for optical navigation algorithms due to extreme lighting conditions, low sun angles, and the distinctive reflectance characteristics of the lunar regolith. By accurately simulating these complex phenomena, the proposed pipeline effectively supports both high-precision landing site evaluation and surface rover exploration in these hazardous regions.

Rendering Framework and Environment Generation: The proposed rendering framework is built within Blender [3] and its physically-based engine, Cycles. Central to this framework is a highly realistic virtual lunar environment designed to reproduce the Moon's optical characteristics, accounting for the effects of surface morphology on illumination and shadowing. As existing Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) often lack the centimetre-level resolution necessary to resolve low-altitude features and rover-scale hazards, high-resolution terrain is generated by synthetically enhancing this data, as done by [4] and [5]. Specifically, the spatial resolution of the base DEMs is first enhanced via fractal synthesis, employing a recursive process that combines the Dia-

mond-Square Random Midpoint Displacement algorithm with Successive Random Additions fractal noise. To further increase realism and simulate the impact history of the surface, procedurally generated craters are superimposed onto the enhanced DEMs, following statistical size-frequency and age distributions, as well as analytical profile and degradation models from impact cratering. Furthermore, metre-scale boulders are integrated into the terrain to reproduce realistic landing and roving hazards.

Beyond morphology, accurately simulating regolith appearance through a Bidirectional Reflectance Distribution Function (BRDF) is crucial for achieving visual fidelity. To this end, a custom Open Shading Language (OSL) shader was developed to implement the Hapke BRDF, based on the formulation presented in [6]. By acknowledging the discrete nature of the regolith and accounting for multiple scattering within the medium, this model accurately reproduces the distinct optical properties of the lunar soil, including porosity effects and the opposition surge at low Sun phase angles. Capturing these phenomena is essential for realistically rendering the extreme lighting environments characteristic of the lunar poles, thereby providing the high-fidelity imagery required for hazard assessment and robust Vision-Based Navigation validation.

Application Scenarios and Results: Figures 1-4 present an overview of rendering results across various locations, camera orientations, and illumination conditions. These examples demonstrate the proposed pipeline's versatility in generating physically consistent optical data across diverse lunar surface scenarios and observation scales, ranging from orbital altitudes down to near-surface perspectives. Specifically, the generated imagery accurately captures the impact of extreme lighting on the visibility of topographical features, successfully simulating the complex shadows cast across the lunar surface (Figs. 1-2). Furthermore, the framework correctly reproduces the opposition surge, where the combined effects of increased reflectance and contrast reduction hide relevant morphological features (Fig. 4). Accounting for these phenomena is vital for evaluating the reliability of hazard detection algorithms in realistic lunar environments, ensuring the success of scientific exploration.

Conclusions: The proposed rendering pipeline provides a versatile platform for generating realistic lunar surface imagery, overcoming the resolution, illumination, and perspective constraints of existing orbital archives. By combining real orbital data with

physically-based procedural generation and photometric modelling, it enables pre-mission assessment of landing safety and surface accessibility, with particular emphasis on the extreme illumination conditions of the lunar poles. In this context, this framework holds strong potential as a tool for the support of mission planning, hazard detection, and autonomous navigation systems validation for future lunar surface exploration.

References: [1] Mathavaraj S. and Negi K. (2025) *J. Spacecraft Rockets*, 62, 159-166. [2] Ishida T., Fukuda S., Kariya K. et al. (2025) *Acta Astronautica*, 226, 772-781. [3] Blender Online Community. (2024) Blender - a 3D modelling and rendering package. <https://www.blender.org/>. [4] Martin I., Parkes S., and Dunstan M. (2014) *IEEE Trans. Aerosp. Electron. Syst.*, 50, 2916-2928. [5] Allan M. et al. (2019) *2019 IEEE Aerospace Conference*, 1-19. [6] Sato H. et al. (2014) *J. Geophys. Res. Planets*, 119, 1775-1805.

Figure 1: View of North Pole from 150 km altitude.

Figure 2: View of Drygalski crater (South Pole) from 150 km altitude.

Figure 3: View of Mare Frigoris from 2 km altitude.

Figure 4: View of Mt. Hadley from Apollo 15 landing site at 50 m above surface, showing the opposition effect.